

EUROPABON

The web database on biodiversity monitoring initiatives at the European level

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WP3 – Task 3.1

IDENTIFYING CURRENT BIODIVERSITY DATA WORKFLOWS ACROSS EUROPE

1.1 GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE DATABASE (TASK 3.1) AND ITS ELEMENTS

We have set up a web-based platform to collect/record the current biodiversity data workflows across Europe. This database will help us understand how biodiversity data collected in monitoring schemes across Europe flows through different institutions and programs and gets processed to produce Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) and Ecosystem Services Indicators (ESS) other EU policy-relevant indicators. From here on, we use the term '**integration initiatives**' to refer to each one of these full biodiversity data workflows. As a reminder here, the **priority is to collect integration initiatives at the European level**, but integration initiatives at other scales (e.g. National) can also be accommodated, particularly if there is a potential to produce a policy-relevant EBV or indicator, or at least the potential to be integrated into other European-level integration initiatives. Some examples of European level biodiversity data workflows are the [reporting of the Habitats](#) and [the Water Framework Directives](#), the [Wild Bird Indicators](#) produced in the Pan-European Common Bird Monitoring Scheme or the [European grassland butterfly indicator](#) produced in the European Butterfly Monitoring Schemes. The set of integration initiatives collected in this database will constitute the information flow network of the EUROPABON project.

There are three main elements in each integration initiative (Figure 1):

1. **IntegrationNodes:** institutions/projects/platforms integrating/processing biodiversity data to generate EBVs, ESS or any other indicators with potential relevance to environmental policy, particularly at the European level. One single integration initiative can be composed of many nodes operating at different scales (e.g. subnational, national, European-level) in a coordinated manner. One single institution can act as an integration node of different integration initiatives.
2. **BiodiversityData:** biodiversity monitoring initiatives responsible for the collection of biodiversity information (data from field observations). The focus of WP3.1 is not to map all monitoring initiatives in Europe, but to ensure that those monitoring initiatives providing data for current biodiversity workflows are well represented in the database.
3. **Datastreams (arrows):** these represent data flows and connect IntegrationNodes across different scales. These contain two types of information: information related to the data flowing between nodes (**dataset**) and whether this has been integrated ("products": EBVs, ESS, indicators) or not (raw and aggregated data) (**data process**). If the data has been integrated/processed, it also contains information about the integration method. A data stream that doesn't connect with another integration node represents a final Product (EBVs, ESS, Indicator) that can eventually be uptaken by policy or not (this is represented in Figure 1 with diamonds of different colours)

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the dataflow across an integration initiative

With this structure in mind, we have built an online platform where we will collect relevant information for the different elements of each integration initiative.

This is the link to the platform: <https://monitoring.europabon.org>

It should lead you to this interface:

These are the guest login credentials:

- Username: europabon
- Password: wp31_europabon

Each contributor to the database will receive a personalized username and password and these will allow him/her to input data of specific integration initiatives. To access the database and to input data for a particular integration initiative, [please add your contact details to this list](#) and you will receive your login details.

For each integration initiative, it is necessary to fill in all the fields within three different tabs (**Integration Nodes**, **Biodiversity Data** and **Data streams** – upper left corner of the website). Within each tab, you will find multiple information fields to be filled; each field is accompanied by an explanation of what type of information it seeks to collect.

The screenshot shows the EUROPABON web interface. On the left is a navigation menu with options: Home, Integration nodes (highlighted with red arrows), BiodiversityData (highlighted with red arrows), All Data streams (highlighted with red arrows), BiodiversityData -> IntegrationNode, IntegrationNode -> IntegrationNode, Products, Search and visualize, and Visualizations. On the right is a schematic diagram titled "Schematic diagram of the dataflow across an integration initiative". The diagram shows a hierarchy of nodes: three green boxes representing BiodiversityData at the bottom, with arrows pointing to three blue circles representing Sub EU-level nodes. These Sub EU-level nodes have arrows pointing to a central blue circle representing the EU node. From the EU node, arrows point to an orange diamond representing Products (EBVs, ESS, indicators) not reaching policy, and a yellow diamond with a blue border representing Products (EBVs, ESS, indicators) uptaken by policy. A legend on the right identifies the symbols: blue circle for IntegrationNodes, green box for BiodiversityData, orange diamond for Products (EBVs, ESS, indicators) not reaching policy, yellow diamond with blue border for Products (EBVs, ESS, indicators) uptaken by policy, and blue arrow for DataStreams.

1) The **Integration Nodes** tab seeks to collect relevant information for each of the nodes within an integration activity (one entry for node – represented with blue circles in Figure 1). Each node is an institution integrating data and/or generating ‘products’ (EBVs, ESS and other indicators). These data and products can flow into another upper-level integration node (e.g. European-level node) or represent ‘final products’ that inform - or could potentially inform - policy. Note here that the hierarchy of integration nodes (the number of sub-European levels) will vary depending on the integration initiative.

The same institution can act as an “integration node” for different integration initiatives. For example, the [European Bird Census Council - EBCC](#) is the European-level integration node of three different integration initiatives: the [European Atlas of Breeding Birds - EBBA2](#), the [EuroBirdPortal - EBP](#) and the [Pan-European Bird Monitoring Scheme - PECBMS](#). In this case, the EBCC will be input as a European-level integration node three times in the database. However, each time this node will contain different information since for example, the details of the main coordinator, the funding available and its origin, or how the data is integrated might differ between integration initiatives carried out by the same institution.

2) The **BiodiversityData** tab seeks to collect information about the field biodiversity monitoring initiatives underneath integration nodes (field data collection). We pursue to create an entry for each monitoring program underneath an integration node but we could group those that follow the same sampling protocol so their data are comparable. For example, we could fill one single “BiodiversityData” entry for all forest inventory plots under a given integration node if all plots are designed and sampled using the same protocols; on the contrary, if the origin of the biodiversity data underneath a given integration node is very diverse (e.g. part of the data comes from systematic plots and part from opportunistic observations) so that the data collected are not comparable, it is required to fill in one “BiodiversityData” entry for each of these groups of uniform data. We suggest you name the “BiodiversityData” using a description of the type of monitoring scheme (please, see the examples of the “BiodiversityData” linked to EBBA2 in the database).

3) The **DataStreams** tab collects information about how is the data processed (if)? and how does it flow? This tab also accommodates information about “products” (EBVs, ESS, indicators) generated by integrationData nodes with potential links to policy (see the example represented with the orange diamond in Figure 1). Therefore, the DataStream tab accommodates information on 1) dataflows between lower-level and upper-level integration nodes (how the products/indicators generated in a lower-level integration node flow into an upper-level integration node; 2) dataflows between

European-level Integration Nodes and Policy and 3) final products from European-level integration nodes that have the potential to inform policy but currently lack that link.

Recording taxonomic information

By building the EuropaBON monitoring database, we seek to map the breadth of taxa for which there are monitoring initiatives already in place across Europe. While we are aware of the complexity of this task (taxonomic classifications are continually being updated), we want to maximize the information collected in this regard. The level of detail of taxonomic information might differ across integration initiatives: some initiatives will be able to provide data at the species level (e.g. the European Atlas of Breeding Birds, the Habitats Directive), while others working with different taxa (e.g. macroinvertebrates) will only be able to record data at the Genus, Family or Order levels.

You will see that in both the “BiodiversityData” and “DataStreams” tabs there is a field called “**Target species**”. Here we ask you to upload a **.csv file** with the list of taxa in a single column. The list of taxa uploaded will be internally normalized against the [GBIF backbone taxonomy](#). Note here that in most integration initiatives, the list of taxa at the level of the monitoring program (“BiodiversityData” tab) will be larger than the list of taxa used by a European-level integration node to generate a product (e.g. the European Butterfly indicator for grassland species focuses on a subset of the whole pool of Butterfly species monitored across Europe). Specifically, we are interested in recording the set of species used to create a given indicator in its most updated version rather than the set of species that would ideally be part of that indicator (for which there might be not enough data to be used in some cases). Ideally, we would like to trace how “data degradation” occurs as the data flow from the monitoring program to the generation of indicators/EBVs at the European level. If the monitoring program recorded is a generalist (e.g. citizen science platforms – iNaturalist, Ornitho) there is no need to upload the list of taxa recorded in that program, but just to indicate the broad taxonomic group of relevance for the integration initiative of interest.

We anticipate it will be hard to map the “taxonomic data degradation” over the full data flow (from the field to policy) within a given integration initiative. However, and ideally, each integration initiative should upload at least the list of taxa integrated to generate an indicator/EBV/ESS (i.e. data stream with origin in European-level integration nodes), and the list of taxa of the monitoring program if this is not generalist (i.e. “BiodiversityData” tab).

Some of the fields within the tabs **IntegrationNodes**, **BiodiversityData** and **DataStreams** are multiple-choice, but you might find that the options available do not fit well the case of the integration activity you are recording. If you want to add a new custom value to the multiple options available, please contact [David Martí](mailto:david.marti@ornitologia.org) with your suggestion (david.marti@ornitologia.org) (the option of adding a new field is unavailable for operative reasons). David is also the contact person for any technical problems that might arise regarding the functioning of the database.

1.2. STEPS TO ENTER DATA OF A GIVEN INTEGRATION INITIATIVE IN THE DATABASE

STEP 1. Make an outline/diagram of the activity you want to enter in the database and identify which are the integration nodes, their hierarchy, how many monitoring programs feed each integration node, what products are generated, etc. Let's exemplify this by having a look at the [European Atlas of Breeding Birds - EBBA2](#). The European-level integration node for this initiative is the [EBCC](#). For this particular initiative, it integrates data from 51 sub-European nodes (many of them - but not all - are National Nodes). Each Sub European-level node passes two types of data to the EBCC (maps of species distribution data at 10 km and at 50 km).

STEP 2. Once you have identified how many nodes your integration initiative has, and how many BiodiversityData programs feed into those nodes, you can start input them into the database. We recommend you start by filling the "BiodiversityData" form
Main Tables > BiodiversityData > Add new BiodiversityData

We pursue to create an entry for each monitoring program underneath an integration node but we could group those that follow the same sampling protocol so their data are comparable. This should be interpreted and input considering the specificities of each integration initiative.

When filling the BiodiversityData form, you'll be asked to provide details about the taxa (main group and species/habitat lists if applicable). If available, we strongly recommend you to upload a general Thesaurus of the taxa involved in that particular initiative, when filling the first BiodiversityData form for that initiative. For the example of the EBBA2, you could select the option "Check this box if you

have a list of taxa to upload...” and then go to the tab “New Thesaurus” to upload the list of 596 species covered by the project.

Taxonomy

Target realm
x Terrestrial x Freshwater x Coastal

Target realm

Target taxa
x Birds

Target taxa

Check this box if you have a list of taxa to upload for this biodiversity data (no need to check it when sending all species available or generalist monitoring programs)

Choose thesaurus ☰ **New thesaurus**

Species thesaurus

Target species

List of the target species/habitats covered by the monitoring initiative (note this is a temporary field and we'll give the option to upload a species lists or select the species from a thesaurus)

Once the general Thesaurus for a project is uploaded, you can assign a list of species to a specific “BiodiversityData” form by “Choose Thesaurus” and making a sub-selection of species collected in each program/country (if applies). This can be done Manually (select manually the species names from the general Thesaurus) or by uploading a list of a species subset (the platform will internally do the matching of the two species lists, ie. the general Thesaurus and the .csv with the subset of species)

Taxonomy

Target realm
x Terrestrial x Freshwater x Coastal

Target realm

Target taxa
x Birds

Target taxa

Check this box if you have a list of taxa to upload for this biodiversity data (no need to check it when sending all species available or generalist monitoring programs)

Choose thesaurus ☰ **New thesaurus**

Species thesaurus
EBBA2 target species

The selected thesaurus includes 596 species. You can:

1. Select all species using the button below.
2. Upload a csv file with the subset of species to be chosen using the button below.
3. Select species manually in the target species select input.

Manually select the species from the full list

Or upload a .csv with the list of species of interest

STEP 3. You can now fill in the form of Integration nodes, starting with the Sub-European-level nodes, as these will be those directly linked to BiodiversityData.

Main tables > Integration Nodes > Add New Integration Node

Main tables

INTEGRATION NODES - LIST

[Add new Integration node](#)

Europe National Subnational Orphan nodes All

Project: Geographic coverage:

Covered countries: Node purpose:

Institution: [Filter](#)

Here you will be asked to provide details the institution doing the integration, the coordinator for that particular project, main funding sources, etc. At the bottom of the form, you will find a field to link each Sub-European-level integration node to its corresponding BiodiversityData source(s).

Linked biodiversity data initiatives

Biodiversity data

.....

Select biodiversity data monitoring projects used by the integration node. No need to select values for upper level integration nodes if biodiversity data is not directly linked. You can create biodiversity data later and edit the field again.

[Show only BiodiversityData linked to geographical coverage](#) [Show all available BiodiversityData initiatives](#)

[Save integration node](#)

Once all Sub-European nodes are entered into the database (51 nodes for the EBBA2 example), you can enter the European-level node (the EBCC for the EBBA2 example). In this case, because the European-level node is not directly linked to BiodiversityData but sources the information to the Sub-European-level nodes, there is no need to fill the field “Linked Biodiversity Data Initiatives”.

STEP 4. Now we need to enter information about how the data flows between nodes and what products are generated. This is done using the “DataStreams” form.

Main Menu > DataStreams > Add new DataStream

Main tables

DATA STREAMS - LIST

[Add new Data stream](#)

All data streams IntegrationNode → IntegrationNode Products BiodiversityData → IntegrationNode (not used anymore)

Project: EBBA2 Data type: Frequency:

Method: [Filter](#)

This form will be used for both:

4.1 Detail how the data flows between integration nodes and integration nodes

AND

4.2 Give information about products generated by the European-level integration node and specify whether these are uptaken by policy or not

For the example of the EBBA2, two DataStreams connect each Sub-European-Level Node to the EBCC: 1) a DataStream for the raw occurrence data at 10 km and 2) a DataStream of aggregated occurrence data at 50 km. This is a total of 51 x 2 data streams. Moreover, the EBBA2 integration initiative has three additional DataStreams with origin in the EBCC (European-level node) that represent “final products” (no uptake by policy yet).

Within each of these DataStreams you have to provide information about the data flowing between nodes and about how the data is processed or the products are generated. If what is generated is an indicator

